

GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource:

Indicators guide 1: Responsible use of indicators

Full resource

Table of contents

Introduction	2
Summary.....	2
Template as part of SCOPE+i Resources and in relation to SCOPE Framework	2
Indicators and metrics	3
Introduction to metrics	3
Commonly used indicators	5
Open science indicators	9
Characteristics of open research infrastructures	10
Visualization tools	11
References	13

Introduction

Summary

This guide provides general guidelines for the use and challenges of indicators. However, different assessment situations always require careful consideration and expertise of metrics and indicators. Mutual reflection of all participants involved in the research assessment (RA) process is important.

Also, open and free research information infrastructures identified in the GraspOS deliverable D2.1 [OS-aware RRA approaches landscape report](#) (Hyrkkänen et al. 2023) and observed by the [GraspOS pilots](#) are introduced. The infrastructures covered include OpenAlex, OpenAIRE, BIP!Services and OpenCitations. The features of these open research information infrastructures demonstrate significant potential for supporting responsible research assessment (RRA) processes. However, further development is needed across all platforms, particularly in their ability to index open science (OS) contributions in research assessment (RA).

Related SCOPE+i Resources:

- Indicators guide 2: Frameworks and toolboxes for open research, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17181862> presents concepts Indicator framework and Indicator toolbox.
- OS indicators as well as FAIR data indicators are explored in the OS assessment guide <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525630>.
- Guide on choosing an assessment method <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525721> discusses weight of qualitative and quantitative methods against the unit to be assessed from macro to micro level.

Template as part of SCOPE+i Resources and in relation to SCOPE Framework

The [SCOPE+i Resources](#) aim to facilitate the transition towards Responsible Research Assessment (RRA) with particular focus on contributions to open science (OS). Being one out of 17 resources (guides, templates and checklists), this toolbox supports the structured organization of research assessment process and information from initial planning through to the publication of assessment protocols.

[SCOPE Framework](#) is a five-stage model for evaluating responsibly. It is a practical step-by-step process designed to help research managers, or anyone involved in conducting research evaluations, in planning new evaluations as well as checking existing evaluations. SCOPE is an acronym, where S stands for START with what you value, C for CONTEXT considerations, O for OPTIONS for evaluating, P for PROBE deeply, and E for EVALUATE your evaluation. This guide is most relevant for the stages O and P.

Figure 1. SCOPE Framework by INORMS (2023) (modified by highlighting the most relevant stages for this resource).

More about SCOPE Framework in International Network of Research Management Societies (INORMS) - Research Evaluation Group (2023). The SCOPE Framework. The University of Melbourne. Report. <https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1>

All SCOPE+i Resources are brought together in the [GraspOS Infrastructure](#) (i), a simple, user-friendly interface (UI) where you can explore project results and save documents to learn and share with others.

Indicators and metrics

Introduction to metrics

Research metrics is a broad concept that encompasses a range of indicators, including those for open science, research collaboration, impact (e.g. citations and downloads) and alignment with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, SDGs, research funding and traditional publication metrics. Publication metrics specifically refers to quantitative analysis of publications resulting in statistical data. [Indicator Themes covered by OpenAIRE Monitor](#) in Figure 2. present the diversity of these metrics.

Figure 2. *Indicator Themes covered by OpenAIRE Monitor.*

Metrics are useful for assessment of big entities like countries and for organizations with qualitative assessment and/or self-assessment on the side. In fact, metrics can be used for all entities in a responsible way. When assessing an individual researcher, the principles of RRA must be considered. Combining both quantitative and qualitative approaches gives a more comprehensive picture of the wholeness.

International recommendations like [Leiden Manifesto](#) and [DORA Guidance on the responsible use of quantitative indicators in research assessment](#) present principles to be applied in research assessment highlighting that publication metrics are used as a part of the overall research assessment and only to support qualitative assessment. Especially responsible publication metrics has become a more widely discussed issue since the publication of the [San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment, DORA](#). The most important take-away of the DORA Declaration is elimination of journal-based metrics in the assessment of an individual researcher. During 2025 [CoARA working group Responsible Metrics and Indicators](#) will publish a recommendation on Responsible use of metrics and indicators in research assessment.

Links:

- <https://www.leidenmanifesto.org/>

Cite as: Sipola, Tiina, & Koivisto, Elina (2025). GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource: Indicators guide 1: Responsible use of indicators. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526168>

- https://sfdora.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/DORA_indicators_guidance.pdf
- <https://sfdora.org/read/>
- DORA (2024), Guidance on the responsible use of quantitative indicators in research assessment. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10979644>

There are no universally applicable rules for using metrics - except in the context of evaluating individual researchers, where caution is especially important. Metrics must always align with the specific purpose of the assessment, which is inherently shaped by the underlying values of the institution.

To ensure fairness and accuracy, it is advisable to use multiple indicators rather than relying on a single metric. This approach helps mitigate the limitations of metrics and data sources. For instance, databases often lack comprehensive coverage across all disciplines, and publication and citation practices vary widely between fields. Emerging forms of scholarly communication, such as preprints and open peer review, further complicate the landscape. Moreover, the classification of scientific fields differs across databases, and data quality issues are common. These factors underscore the importance of contextual knowledge when interpreting and presenting metric-based results. When using metrics and indicators openness, transparency, reliability and reproducibility of data and methods are essential. Openness and transparency become possible by using free-of-charge databases instead of commercial databases.

Crucially, metrics tend to reflect past performance and rarely capture the full scope or future potential of research. They often overlook essential dimensions such as OS practices, teaching contributions, interdisciplinary collaboration, and societal impact. Indicators for these areas are still underdeveloped or entirely absent in most databases.

Ultimately, RA must go beyond metrics. A holistic, values-driven approach that incorporates both qualitative and quantitative inputs is essential for capturing the richness and diversity of scholarly work. Qualitative assessment offers more contextual understanding of research than any single indicator can provide.

Commonly used indicators

Table 1. provides examples and guidance for the use of metrics and indicators. While metrics can offer valuable insights, their use is accompanied by significant challenges and limitations particularly when assessing individual researchers or a very small set of publications. The table is compiled using many sources, e.g.:

- EOSC / FAIR-impact. [Metrics for data](https://fair-impact.eu/metrics-data) (<https://fair-impact.eu/metrics-data>)
- Elsevier [SciVal LibGuide: Metrics & Indicators](https://elsevier.libguides.com/c.php?g=1328583&p=9781971) (<https://elsevier.libguides.com/c.php?g=1328583&p=9781971>)
- [Finnish national guide to publication metrics](https://wiki.eduuni.fi/spaces/csckjmo/pages/195134729/Finnish+national+guide+to+publication+metrics) (<https://wiki.eduuni.fi/spaces/csckjmo/pages/195134729/Finnish+national+guide+to+publication+metrics>) maintained by the Finn-ARMA's publications metrics network and [KJMO-project group](https://wiki.eduuni.fi/spaces/csckjmo/pages/338181281/Oppaan+tekij%C3%A4t+The+authors+of+the+guide) (<https://wiki.eduuni.fi/spaces/csckjmo/pages/338181281/Oppaan+tekij%C3%A4t+The+authors+of+the+guide>)
- InCites [Indicators Handbook](https://incites.zendesk.com/hc/en-gb/sections/22667074311953-Indicators-Handbook) (<https://incites.zendesk.com/hc/en-gb/sections/22667074311953-Indicators-Handbook>)

Cite as: Sipola, Tiina, & Koivisto, Elina (2025). GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource: Indicators guide 1: Responsible use of indicators. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526168>

Table 1. Examples of commonly used indicators.

Type	Indicator (example)	Use cases, challenges, considerations	Read more
Productivity indicators	Number of research outputs e.g. publications	<p>Mainly for publications.</p> <p>Publishing is only one part of a researcher’s work. The sum of publications alone does not indicate the excellence of the individual researcher or vice versa.</p> <p>Publishing practices like publication types (article, monograph) and co-authorship differ from field to field.</p> <p>The sum of research outputs depends on what source is used. Databases do not cover disciplines and publication types equally.</p> <p>Should be used only to support quantitative and expert evaluation.</p>	
Citation impact indicators	Citations	<p>Based on the number of publications and citations.</p> <p>The citation time window should be clearly indicated.</p> <p>Consider an open-ended citation window instead of a short as short window highlights publications that are most debated at the time of publication.</p> <p>Outliers affect the total sum of citations. Outliers are values within a dataset that vary greatly from the others—they’re either much larger, or significantly smaller.</p> <p>Citation patterns differ between fields. Citation count is not comparable between subject fields, domains or disciplines.</p> <p>Can be only used for benchmarking entities of similar size and disciplines.</p> <p>Citations take a long time to accumulate and value depends on the used database.</p> <p>When citations are used as article-level metrics, they reflect the influence of an article but not necessarily quality. Critical</p>	<p>Smart Citations scite is a tool that displays the context of the citations and describes whether the article provides supporting or contracting evidence. Use is subject to a charge.</p> <p>https://scite.ai/</p>

Cite as: Sipola, Tiina, & Koivisto, Elina (2025). GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource: Indicators guide 1: Responsible use of indicators. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526168>

		citations versus supportive ones are not usually distinguished.	
Citation impact indicators	H-index	<p>Indicates a balance between publication productivity (scholarly output) and citations to publications. E.g. An h-index value of 10 means that a researcher has 10 publications that all have at least 10 citations.</p> <p>Is not suitable for assessment of individual researchers.</p> <p>Favors senior researchers.</p> <p>Value can be greater than the number of publications.</p> <p>Value depends on what source is used.</p>	<p>Read more Bihari, A., Tripathi, S., & Deepak, A. (2023). A review on h-index and its alternative indices. <i>Journal of Information Science</i>, 49(3), 624-665.</p> <p>https://doi.org/10.1177/01655515211014478</p>
Citation impact indicators	Field normalized citation indicators	<p>The average ratio of citations received relative to the expected world average for the subject field, publication type and publication year.</p> <p>The world average is 1. Values below this threshold indicate a lower than average number of citations while values above 1.0 indicate a number of citations that is higher than average.</p> <p>Tries to correct for differences in citation patterns from one field to another. Takes into account the field of science, age and type of publication.</p> <p>Can be used for single articles or a set of publications. As outliers can affect the value of the field weighted citation indicator of a publication set, consider presenting indicators for each publication individually.</p>	

		Unreliable when based on a small number of papers.	
Indicators for evaluating journals	Journal Impact Factor, JIF	<p>Available in Journal Citation Reports based on Web of Science database/Clarivate.</p> <p>Calculated by dividing the number of citations in the Journal Citation Reports year (the numerator) by the total number of citable items published in the two previous years (the denominator). Take into account only articles and review articles.</p> <p>Does not indicate the quality of a research article.</p> <p>According to principles of RRA use of JIF or any other journal-based metrics is prohibited when assessing individual researchers.</p>	
Societal impact indicators, altmetrics	Downloads, mentions, attention	<p>Article level metrics indicates e.g. attention, downloads and mentions in social media and mass media.</p> <p>Current issues dominate and receive more attention.</p> <p>Accumulation starts immediately when research output is published.</p> <p>Attention from different sources have different coefficient e.g. in Altmetric.com.</p> <p>Permanent identifier like DOI necessary in calculation.</p>	
Economic impact indicators	Patents	<p>Patent citations and patent cited publications can indicate societal and economic impact of research.</p> <p>Patent citations can be useful e.g. for competitive analysis or benchmarking and exploring technology trends.</p>	

Cite as: Sipola, Tiina, & Koivisto, Elina (2025). GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource: Indicators guide 1: Responsible use of indicators. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526168>

Open science indicators	Open science	<p>The majority of open science activities are not reported and registered in databases.</p> <p>Most databases offer possibilities to explore OA-publications but some are not able to register OA- publications which are open through self-archiving.</p>	<p>Explore also Open science assessment guide</p> <p>https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525630</p>
Collaboration indicators	Collaboration based on authorship	<p>Collaboration can be explored e.g. by looking at the affiliations of authors in publications.</p> <p>E.g. the number or proportion of single author publications, international co-publications and company collaboration.</p>	
FAIR data indicators	FAIR metrics	<p>Indicators for findability, accessibility, interoperability and reusability for research data e.g. sum of published metadata of research, data sum of published data (sets).</p> <p>Data citations.</p> <p>Tracing published metadata and data citations is challenging due to the nature of research data. Moreover, data - though an important research output - is not yet fully recognized. Knowledge of data management and citation practices remains limited, conventions for citing data are not well established, and indexing services are still under development.</p>	

OS-aware RRA approaches landscape report by [Hyrkkänen et al \(2023\)](#) presents a wide selection of quantitative indicators and metrics for research outputs. Metrics is explored on:

- research output level (Table 6.1, starting from page 71)
- individual researcher level (Table 6.2, starting from page 74)
- open science (Table 6.3, starting from page 75)
- entity level (Table 6.4, page 77)

Overview of indicators and metrics at the country level based on the SuperMoRRI Monitoring Report (Losinno et al. 2020) is presented in Table 6.5.(starting from page 77).

Open science indicators

Open science metrics are commonly based on the share of outputs available in open access, measured at the level of researchers, publications, or institutions. Dataset indicators often require compliance with FAIR principles, while in open education metrics can include the number of open

Cite as: Sipola, Tiina, & Koivisto, Elina (2025). GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource: Indicators guide 1: Responsible use of indicators. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526168>

courses, educational resources, or related events. Career-level indicators follow responsible metrics principles (e.g., Metric Tide, Leiden Manifesto, DORA) and focus on aspects such as contributorship and co-author statements. Examples of these indicators are summarized in Hyrkkänen et al. (2023, p. 75; Table 6.3).

Coverage of OA journals varies between databases. Maddi A. et al. (2025) have studied the geographical and disciplinary coverage of OA journals in three databases: OpenAlex, Scopus and the Web of Science (WoS). Based on the results OpenAlex indexes a larger number of OA journals compared to Scopus or WoS. OpenAlex also provides a broader global coverage of journals. Indexing policy is important as visibility of OA research can shift significantly across countries and disciplines.

Explore also:

- [Plan S compliance indicators](#) in OpenAIRE.
- [PathOS Open Science Indicator Handbook](#) which covers various aspects of measuring open science itself, but also delves into reproducibility and impact. For example, the chapter [“Evaluation of open science in research assessment”](#) throws out interesting questions for institutions like *What variety of Open Science practices are taken into consideration in research assessment?* or *How open are institutions in sharing such information on their hiring policies?*
- Hrynaszkiwicz, Iain; Kiermer, Veronique (2022). PLOS Open Science Indicators principles and definitions. Figshare. Preprint. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.21640889.v1> . PLOS journals support OS practices with a “core set” of practices that are supported by every PLOS journal
- PLOS open science indicators in Public Library of Science (2022). PLOS Open Science Indicators. Public Library of Science. Dataset. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.21687686.v8>

Characteristics of open research infrastructures

Hyrkkänen et. al. (2023, p. 97) note that research assessment can draw on both global and local publication databases. Commercial platforms like Scopus, Web of Science, and Dimensions are widely used, but since assessment should remain under control of the academic community, the authors highlight the importance of non-profit and EU-funded platforms which offer a variety of indicators to be used in RA.

The use of OpenAIRE, OpenAlex, BIP!Services and OpenCitations is free to charge and aligns with the [Barcelona Declaration](#) (barcelona-declaration.org) which advocates for the use of open and publicly available data sources and databases. Support and interoperability with permanent identifiers such as DOI and ORCID is possible for the four infrastructures enabling reliable and consistent linking of research outputs and contributors.

Table 2. illustrates shortly the characteristics of OpenAIRE, OpenAlex, BIP!Services and OpenCitations including metrics.

Cite as: Sipola, Tiina, & Koivisto, Elina (2025). GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource: Indicators guide 1: Responsible use of indicators. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526168>

Table 2. Characteristics of OpenAIRE Graph and Explorer, OpenAlex, BIP!Services and OpenCitations.

Infrastructure	OpenAIRE Graph	OpenAIRE Explore	OpenAlex	BIP!Services	OpenCitations (COCI)
Producer / Origin	OpenAIRE Project	OpenAIRE Project	Non-profit	Athena RC Project	The Research Centre for Open Scholarly Metadata, an independent research centre within the University of Bologna. (non-profit)
Access /	graph.openaire.eu	explore.openaire.eu	openalex.org	bip.imsi.athenarc.gr	opencitations.net
Data Sources	DOAJ, Crossref, Unpaywall, ORCID, MAG, Datacite; repositories (OpenDOAR, re3data, FAIRSharing, EOSC, Zenodo, ArXiv, etc.);	Built on OpenAIRE Graph	ORCID, ROR, DOAJ, Unpaywall, PubMed, PMC, ISSN, Internet Archive, web crawls, institutional and subject specific repositories such as repositories arXiv and Zenodo	OpenAIRE Graph, OpenCitations COCI, MAG, Crossref	Crossref open DOI-to-DOI citations
Entities / Coverage	Research products, organizations, projects (with funders & funding)	Same as OpenAIRE Graph	Works (articles, books, datasets), authors, sources, institutions, topics, publishers, funders	Articles with metadata (DOI, authors, year, venue, citations); topics from OpenAlex	Open DOI citation index
Update Frequency	Monthly	Mirrors Graph updates	Monthly snapshot; hourly via API	Not specified	1–3 months
Features & Indicators	Citation-based impact indicators; usage statistics; free API	User-friendly search; filters (access, type, funder, SDGs, etc.); sorting (date, citations, popularity, influence, impulse)	Topic tagging; full open snapshot, API access; bibliometric statistics	BIP! Indicators aligned with DORA/CoARA	Free open citation database (COCI)
Pros	Comprehensive EU-driven infrastructure; rich entity linking; free programmatic	Easy to use; rich filters; good entry point for non-technical users	Fully open; frequent updates; structured snapshot & API	Indicators tailored for responsible metrics; integrates multiple open data sources	100% open; transparent; widely reusable
Cons	Requires technical skills for API use	May not be as comprehensive as Graph API; limited customization	Works are tagged with topics (~4500) using an automated system that takes into account available information about the work, including title, abstract, source (journal) name and citations.		Limited to Crossref DOIs

Visualization tools

Graphs and maps support interpretation of bibliometric data e.g. helping to understand the factors behind the data. Visualization also shows trends and outliers especially within large data sets. The effect of outlier on a value - e.g. total sum of citations - can be big.

Below examples of tools for visualization of data.

VOSviewer

- [VOSviewer - Visualizing scientific landscapes](#)
- By CWTS, Leiden
- VOSviewer is a tool for building and visualizing bibliometric and text-mining networks based on citations, co-authorship, or term co-occurrence.

Gephi

- [Gephi - The Open Graph Viz Platform](#)

Cite as: Sipola, Tiina, & Koivisto, Elina (2025). GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource: Indicators guide 1: Responsible use of indicators. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526168>

- Open-source
- Free
- Read more Bastian, M., Heymann, S., & Jacomy, M. (2009). Gephi: An Open Source Software for Exploring and Manipulating Networks. Proceedings of the International AAAI Conference on Web and Social Media, 3(1), 361-362.
<https://doi.org/10.1609/icwsm.v3i1.13937>

CiteSpace

- [CiteSpace: visualizing patterns and trends in scientific literature](#)
- Free
- By Chen C.
- CiteSpace is a freely available Java application for visualizing and analysing trends and patterns in scientific literature.
- Download [CiteSpace Home](#)

SciNoBo - Open Science Knowledge Graph

- [SciNoBo: Science No Borders - SciLake](#)
- SciLake goal is to increase discoverability and reproducibility of open scientific content
- SciLake builds upon the OpenAIRE ecosystem and EOSC services to enable creation, interlinking, and maintenance of Science Knowledge Graphs (SKGs) and execution of data science and graph mining queries on top of them unlock the vast scientific knowledge space with advanced, AI-based services that exploit customized perspectives.
- SciNoBo platform is a valuable resource for science communities engaged in open science practices. With its wide range of tools and functionalities, researchers can explore and analyse publications, classify research fields, detect claims and conclusions, analyse citations, and classify publications. By leveraging the power of large language models and access to diverse data sources, SciNoBo provides an intuitive and immersive platform for researchers to interact with the scientific community and gain valuable insights from scientific literature.

References

Hyrkkänen (2023). Anna-Kaisa Hyrkkänen, Dragan Ivanović, Janne Pölönen, Marita Kari, & Elina Pylvänäinen. (2023). GraspOS Deliverable D2.1 "OS-aware RRA approaches landscape report". Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11098095>

International Network of Research Management Societies (INORMS) - Research Evaluation Group (2023). The SCOPE Framework. The University of Melbourne. Report. <https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1>

Losinno, M. G, Ryan, T. K. & Mejlgaard, N. (2020). D2.2: 1st Responsible Research and Innovation Monitoring Report. SUPER MoRRI <https://super-morri.eu/findings/>

Maddi A, Maisonobe M, Boukacem-Zeghmouri C (2025) Geographical and disciplinary coverage of open access journals: OpenAlex, Scopus, and WoS. PLoS ONE 20(4): e0320347. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0320347>